

Capacity of the Ethiopian Primary Health Care System for Achieving Universal Health Coverage: A Primary Health Care Progression Approach

Running Head: the Primary Health Care Capacity in Ethiopia

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Abstract

Comprehensive and globally comparable evidence about the Primary Health Care (PHC) capacity is needed to inform policies and decisions. We carried out a study to assess the Ethiopian PHC capacity in terms of governance, inputs, and population health and facility management domains. The PHC capacity of all the regions, city administrations, and the Ministry of Health was assessed using the PHC progression model. The model has 33 measures categorized into three domains. Data were collected and synthesized from all relevant national and regional documents, datasets, and key informants. A team of trained evaluation experts conducted external assessments at national and regional levels followed by an internal assessment and a validation workshop. All 33 measures were scored from 1 (lowest) to 4 (highest). The inter-rater reliability test indicated that the overall agreement between internal and external scores was 65%. We have found the highest consistency in the internal assessment with a score of 0.84. The findings of this study indicated that the governance domain score was 2.8 out of 4, showing varying scores in quality management, priority setting as well as innovation and learning. The inputs domain score was 2.3 with drugs, supplies, and facility infrastructure. The score for the population health and facility management domain was 2. A comparison of federal and national average scores for all measures indicated no significant difference between the two (p -value = 0.69). There are relevant PHC policies and leadership structures at the federal and regional levels. However, the capacity to effectively implement these policies and strategies at sub-national levels is sub-optimal. The challenges related to major inputs coupled with data quality problems reduced the capacity of the PHC system at the local level. Periodic assessment of the PHC system and closely working with subnational units potentially improves the capacity of PHC in Ethiopia.

Introduction

The major causes of morbidity and mortality in low- and middle-income countries, including Ethiopia, remain largely preventable (Lelieveld, Haines and Pozzer, 2018; Reiner *et al.*, 2020) (Bauserman *et al.*, 2020). According to the Global Burden of Disease reports, Ethiopia's communicable, maternal, neonatal, and nutritional disorders accounted for over 43% of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) lost and 51% of premature deaths in 2015 (Incidence and Collaborators, 2016). Increasing trend in the incidence and prevalence of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) added burden to the already strained health system. In 2015, NCDs accounted for 49% of DALYs and 41% of years of life lost due to premature death (Incidence and Collaborators, 2016; Misganaw *et al.*, 2017). The experience of countries indicated that all these deaths and disabilities could be significantly reduced with a well-structured healthcare system, especially at the grassroots level (Kruk *et al.*, 2018).

Primary health care (PHC) is a pillar of the important policy foundation, universal health coverage, which helps improve the well-being of all people and reduces inequitable access to healthcare (Dwinantoaji *et al.*, 2022). After the introduction of the PHC approach, preventive and promotive services supplemented by basic curative care at the community level and nearby health facilities have resulted in a significant reduction in illness and death, especially in developing countries (Sachs, 2012). Globally, the PHC approach helped many countries to raise health service coverage and achieve health and health-related indicators (Walker and Peterson, 2021). It is an effective approach to address all members of society at their place of residence at an affordable cost. The PHC framework involves managing and providing services based on efficient, equitable, cost-effective and patient-centered mechanisms. This approach has supported many countries' journey toward universal health coverage (Walker and Peterson, 2021).

Even though PHC was initiated more than four decades back to achieve universal health coverage worldwide, according to the WHO, at least half of the world's people do not receive the health services they need. The WHO is currently focusing on and supporting countries in the Sustainable Development Goals target 3.8 to achieve universal health coverage in 2030 (Hussein, 2015; Arredondo, Recamán and Castrejón, 2020). There have been efforts nationally to increase universal health coverage using PHC as a tool. The introduction of the health extension program and volunteer community health services are good examples (Woldie *et al.*, 2018). Although there are progresses, Ethiopia is far behind in achieving the UHC in terms of access to quality essential health services and universal access to safe, effective, quality and affordable essential medicines (Tadesse *et al.*, 2021).

Ethiopia started integrating the PHC principles into its health system soon after the Alma Ata declaration (World Health Organization, 2019). The PHC principles are reflected in all past and present policies and strategic plans. Currently, the country's health system, in general, and PHC, in particular, are being guided by the Health Sector Transformation Plan (HSTP) (Ethiopian Ministry of Health, 2015). The planning of PHC has been guided by a health care delivery plan known as the Woreda-Based Health Sector Plan (WBHSP). The WBHSP is an evidence-based planning approach that consists of collaborative approaches to "top-down" and "bottom-up" planning along the health administration ladder (Ministry of Health, 2017a). The successes of the country in meeting national and international goals are primarily associated with this community health service delivery structure under the PHC (Wang *et al.*, 2016).

Assessing the capacity of health systems is essential not only to understand the status of the health system but also to evaluate capacity-strengthening efforts. However, capacity assessment is often a complex process that requires well-validated frameworks. Furthermore, there is a lack of quality data to monitor the health system's capacity and performance in Ethiopia (Adane *et al.*, 2021; Tilahun *et al.*, 2021). The Primary Health Care Performance Initiative (PHCPI) has developed a framework called the Vital Signs Profile (VSP) to help measure the capacity, financing, performance and equity of PHC activities (PHCPI, 2018f). Among the components of VSP, we measured the capacity of PHC in this study. Even though studies have been conducted to assess health system capacity in Ethiopia (Sudhakar *et al.*, 2017; Assefa *et al.*, 2020), up-to-date evidence of current capacity from an assessment at the PHC level is needed. Moreover, there are noticeable capacity gaps in the Ethiopian PHC system (Fubstetter, 2016; Dejene *et al.*, 2019). The measurement approaches for the capacity are also outdated and not standardized. As a result, it has been a challenge to identify areas of intervention for improvement. This study aimed to measure the capacity of PHC in Ethiopia to assess how the PHC system is progressing toward an optimized capacity for delivery of effective PHC using the PHCPI methods and tools, through a recent and standardized model called the "PHC progression model". The study also examined the variations in PHC capacity assessment scores among regions.

Methods and Materials

Study context

Ethiopia is the second most populous country in Africa, with a total population of about 110 million in 2021 (Central Statistical Agency, 2013). This assessment covered nine regions (Afar, Amhara, Oromia, Benishangul-Gumuz, Southern Nations, Nationalities and Peoples [SNNP], Somali, Sidama, and Harari) and two city administrations (Addis Ababa and Dire Dawa).

The Ethiopian government has been investing in health system strengthening for many years. The country's health care is structured in a three-tier system, which includes primary, secondary, and tertiary levels of care. The primary level of care includes services delivered in 353 primary hospitals, 3735 health centers (HCs), 17550 health posts (HPs), and a community outreach program (Mann *et al.*, 2017; Ethiopian Public Health Institute, 2018). The primary health care unit (PHCU) contains five satellite HPs (the lowest-level facility in the health system, at the village level) and a referral HC. This is the point where PHC is administered and primary services are facilitated under the health service delivery structure (WHO-Unicef, 1978; Ministry of Health, 2020c). Ethiopia's Health Extension Program (HEP), operated under the PHC system, is based at the HPs and involves 39,878 health extension workers (HEWs) (Wang *et al.*, 2016).

PHC capacity measurement tool and measures

We used the PHC-VSP model to measure the capacity of the Ethiopian PHC. The PHC-VSP provides a snapshot of PHC systems in individual countries, shining a light on areas where systems are strong and have challenges (Ratcliffe *et al.*, 2019). It is designed to help countries and development partners identify priority areas for improvement and to track and trend improvements over time. The VSP assesses different areas of the health system that are important for providing quality PHC for all, categorized into four vital signs. This comprehensive profile involves assessing the financing, capacity, equity and performance of the primary health system in the nation. This assessment was done between April and May 2021.

The capacity domain of the PHC-VSP assesses three critical aspects of the PHC: governance, inputs, and population health and facility management. The capacity assessment tool used in this study has 33 measures (Ratcliffe *et al.*, 2019). These 33 measures of PHC capacity included eight measures of governance, 16 measures of health system inputs, and nine measures of population health and health facility management. Each measure was rated from level one to four based on pre-defined criteria adapted from the PHC progression model. One represents the least capacity and four represents the highest capacity (Ratcliffe *et al.*, 2019).

We used three sources of information in this assessment: documents from various sources, key informants who are leaders and experienced experts in their respective directorates in the ministry and regional health bureaus, and secondary data from reports and databases (Table 1).

Table 1: Domains of PHC capacity and major data sources

Domain	Sub-domain	Major data sources
Governance	Governance and Leadership	National Health Policy, HSTP I&II, Roadmap for Optimizing the Ethiopian Health Extension, Essential Health Services Package of Ethiopia, woreda-based plans, and various guidelines and studies
	Adjustment to Population Health Needs	Health and Health-related Indicators 2017, Mini DHS 2019, PHEM Guidelines 2012, HSTP I&II, woreda-based plans, annual performance reports
Inputs	Drugs and Supplies	SARA 2018 data and report, annual performance reports, on-site records
	Facility Infrastructure	SARA 2018 data and report, Health and Health-related Indicators report, regional reports
	Information Systems	Roadmap for Optimizing the Ethiopian Health Extension, CHIS Data Recording and Reporting 2011, annual performance reports
	Workforce	National HR for Health Strategy 2016, annual performance reports, Directive on CPD for Health Professionals 2013, Health Professionals Registration and Licensing Directive 2014, HEP implementation guideline
	Funds	Ethiopian public expenditure review, Ethiopia Health Sector Financing Reform report, annual performance reports, Ethiopia's Progress in Health Financing and the Contribution of the 1998 Health Care and Financing Strategy
Population Health and Facility Management	Population Health Management	CHIS Data Recording and Reporting 2011, Roadmap for Enhancing the Implementation of One Plan, One Budget and One Report in Ethiopia 2012
	Facility Organization and Management	Assessment of Health Management Information System (HMIS) Performance 2014, CHIS Data Recording and Reporting 2011, Ethiopian National Health Care Quality Strategy, Health Data Quality Review 2018

Methods of PHC capacity assessment

The assessment process included an internal assessment by PHC stakeholders, external assessments by teams of evaluators, and a validation workshop. This process was preceded by collecting and synthesizing evidence related to each of the 33 measures.

The PHC capacity assessment team first reviewed the information obtained from all secondary sources and then identified the information gaps to complete the questions included in the PHC capacity

assessment tool. The team also organized key informant interviews with the experts and officials in the Ministry of Health (MOH) or regional health bureaus to acquire any remaining information.

Secondary data analysis: We obtained secondary data related to surveillance and most facility inputs from the Service Availability and Readiness Assessment (SARA) database of the Ethiopian Public Health Institute (EPHI) (Ethiopian Public Health Institute, 2018). We also used the Health Management Information System (HMIS) databases in different regions and at the MOH for population health and facility management issues.

Document review and synthesis: One PHC capacity assessment team composed of two or three members was assigned to each of the nine regions, the two city administrations and the MOH. Each regional/city and MOH assessment team reviewed national and regional policy documents, national and regional strategic plans, national and regional surveys, performance reports, guidelines, manuals, and similar documents. The team collected relevant data using a template prepared for the assessment.

Key informant interviews: After conducting the secondary data analysis and document review, the team of assessors carefully identified information gaps and those indicators that needed further verification and explanation. The team then identified key informants after carefully mapping potential key informants who could give relevant information. The interviews with key informants were tape-recorded and transcribed for use in the data analysis and synthesis.

The findings from each data source were synthesized in a single document using a data extraction template prepared for the assessment. The results from each data sources were written separately and the sources of information were indicated. The qualitative and quantitative data from different sources were written independently for each of the 33 measures using a data synthesis template obtained from the PHCPI. All the regional/city and MOH assessment teams used this document for their evaluations and to complete the scoring sheet of the PHC capacity measurement tool.

External assessment

A total of 32 capacity assessors were recruited for this assessment. All assessors were master's degree and Ph.D. holders in health systems management, health monitoring and evaluation, or health service administration. All of them had at least three years of experience in the country's health systems or were teaching health systems at a university. Before the assessment, the capacity assessors had ten days of workshops with the investigators on capacity assessment tools, document review methods, and ethical principles. The assessors, under close support and supervision, piloted the capacity assessment tool and method in the Addis Ababa health bureau for three days.

The capacity assessors did the national and regional/city levels PHC capacity assessment using a tool prepared by the PHCPI for this purpose. The team collected relevant data from their respective assigned regions. The collected information was synthesized using a template designed for the purpose. The synthesis document was prepared from the desk review, qualitative interviews, and secondary analysis of quantitative data. All the collected information from different sources was synthesized into a single document. Based on the synthesis, each assessment team member scored each capacity assessment measure independently. Each process was concluded by producing reports containing assessment scores

and detailed narratives. The teams then used the Delphi technique (Sharkey and Sharples, 2001) to build agreement among themselves.

Internal/self-assessment

A team of experts with a direct link with PHC was organized in each regional health bureaus and at the MOH. All team members were working in the regional/city administration health system and had a role in PHC systems at the time of the assessment. In the case of the MOH, eight participants were invited. With minimal variability across regions, the team comprised individuals from relevant units in each region. In addition to experts working in the MOH, the internal assessors' team in the ministry included four representatives from partner organizations who were directly involved in the Ethiopian PHC system. The regional team included 16–18 experts from the regional health bureau, and 6–8 experts represented lower administrative units like zones, districts, and PHC facilities.

The internal assessors attended a workshop at their assigned region facilitated by the evaluation experts. They attended a one-day training on PHC capacity assessment and capacity assessment measures. Following the training, the external capacity assessors presented the synthesized information to the team of internal capacity assessors for two consecutive days. Over the following two days, the internal assessors measured the capacity of the respective regions' PHCs and gave a score for all 33 measures.

In the internal capacity assessment process, each internal assessor silently gave a score of 1 to 4 for each of the measures. The meeting facilitators collected, summarized and presented all the scores provided by the internal assessors. They discussed the scores after the presentation. Finally, they built a consensus and came up with a single capacity score for all 33 measures.

The validation processes

Some differences between the internal and external assessment results were observed in all the regions and the MOH. The validation workshop was meant to resolve these differences and enrich the narrative summaries. The internal and external assessment teams in each region and the MOH met to discuss the convergence/divergence of the scores between the internal and external assessments and reached a consensus on the final scores. The scores from the internal and external assessments were presented along with the consensus scores. A one-day consensus-building (validation) workshop was held in each region and at the MOH.

Analysis and synthesis

The external assessment team synthesized relevant information from evidence synthesis, secondary data analysis, and qualitative data analysis based on the 33 measures. This information was summarized and organized into one document for reference in the internal and external assessments. The internal and external assessment teams scored the 33 PHC capacity measures based on this evidence summary. The scores were recorded in an Excel file. These scores were then summarized into nine sub-domains and three domains of PHC capacity assessment. In this article, we present the summarized findings for each domain and sub-domain of the assessment. The inter-rater reliability between internal, external and final scores was described using agreement statistics, and internal consistency among the measures was examined using Cronbach's alpha.

Inter-rater reliability and internal consistency

The overall agreement between internal and external scores was 65%, although this varied between 51.5% in SNNPR and 78.8% in Afar. Internal scores had a higher agreement with final scores (83.3%) compared to external scores (78.3%). The inter-rater agreement was particularly low in Dire Dawa (Table 2).

Table 2: Agreement (%) between internal, external and final scores

Regions	Internal vs External	Internal vs Final	External vs Final
National	78.8	97.0	81.8
Addis Ababa	60.6	75.8	78.8
Afar	78.8	84.8	93.9
Amhara	75.8	78.8	93.9
Benishangul-Gumuz	75.8	87.9	81.8
Dire Dawa	39.4	84.8	48.5
Gambella	60.6	87.9	69.7
Harar	69.7	78.8	90.9
Oromia	66.7	78.8	84.8
Sidama	60.6	84.8	69.7
SNNPR	51.5	75.8	69.7
Somali	60.6	84.8	75.8
Overall	64.9	83.3	78.3

The overall internal consistency among the sub-domains of the capacity assessment was 0.84. The inputs domain had higher internal consistency compared to the other domains. As with the findings of inter-rater reliability, internal assessment scores had higher internal consistency than external assessment scores (Table 3).

Table 3: Internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha) for scores by domain and sub-domain

Domains and sub-domains	# of items	Internal	External	Final
Governance	8	0.73	0.52	0.73
Governance and Leadership	5	0.70	0.40	0.67
Adjustment to Population Health Needs	3	0.79	0.49	0.47
Inputs	16	0.91	0.86	0.91
Drugs and Supplies	3	0.88	0.93	0.93
Facility Infrastructure	3	0.85	0.66	0.85
Information Systems	3	0.10	NA*	0.36
Workforce	4	0.55	0.55	0.54
Funds	3	0.82	0.85	0.76
Population Health and Facility Management	9	0.69	0.70	0.71
Population Health Management	4	0.66	0.70	0.66
Facility Organization and Management	5	0.46	0.51	0.49
All sub-domains	9	0.86	0.65	0.84

*The score for civil registration and vital statistics items was constant

Results

Capacity of Ethiopian Primary Health Care by Domains

The Ethiopian PHC system has been the main preventive, promotive and basic curative service delivery hub for most of the country's population. The system has been improving in several instances, although there are several challenges. We have described Ethiopia's PHC in terms of governance, inputs and population health and facility management as follows:

Governance

In Ethiopia, the PHC system has a pivotal role in creating policy and associated documents, strategies, and plans. The health policy of the Transitional Government of Ethiopia, the Health Sector Transformation Plan (HSTP), the Healthcare Financing Strategy, and other program-specific strategic documents, including the Health Extension Program Optimization Roadmap, emphasize the principles and components of PHC as their central feature. However, a strategy providing comprehensive guidance regarding its provision, financing, regulation, and objectives is not yet available. The policies and strategies have created an enabling environment, but they are insufficient for local authorities and health facilities to make essential PHC services available for their catchment populations.

Regarding leadership structure, at the federal level, there is a national PHC coordinating authority called the PHC and HEP Directorate. This directorate coordinates, monitors, integrates, and implements national PHC strategies and policies. It is also mandated to oversee regional PHC activities. With some variations in structure and accountability, all the regions and city administrations have PHC coordinating units. This structure continues to the zonal and district levels with some variations across regions.

The Ethiopian government took several measures to raise the quality, multi-sectoral action and social accountability of the PHC service at the national and sub-national levels. The implementation of the National Quality Strategy (2015–2020), the following Healthcare Quality and Safety Strategy (2021–2025), and the Primary Healthcare Alliance for Quality (EPAQ) are a few initiatives among all (Ministry of Health, 2017b, 2020b). Multi-sectoral action is another focus area of the Ethiopian PHC. For instance, the HEP roadmap and the implementation of the HEP in the country allow the engagement of community-level social structures and the realization of multi-sectoral action at the *Kebele* [smallest administrative unit] level through a functional collaborative framework (Ministry of Health, 2020c). The MOH harmonization manual and the second Health Sector Transformation Plan (HSTP II) have various goals that bring different stakeholders from the government, non-governmental organizations, the community, civil society and other relevant stakeholders (Ministry of Health, 2007).

Ethiopia's PHC governance is encountered with challenges that include limited participation of the private sector and civil society in developing policies and standards for the entire health system. This results in variations in quality and performance measurement and evaluation methods among private and public health facilities. Furthermore, the health and health-related information at the private PHC facilities are not collected the way that the public facility information are collected.

Inputs

According to the 2018 service availability and readiness assessment (SARA), there are several shortages of medicine, equipment and supplies across the country's PHC facilities. For instance, none of the health facilities had all 24 essential medicines; on average, facilities had four of the six tracer items of basic equipment, and the mean availability of diagnostic capacity tests ranged from two out of eight in Oromia to six out of eight in the Harari region. Only 1% of facilities had all seven basic amenity tracer items, with a mean availability of 39%. The mean availability of standard precautions and infection prevention items was 42% (Ethiopian Public Health Institute, 2018). On the other hand, access to primary health coverage increased from 50.7% in 2000 to more than 90% in 2019 (Ministry of Health, 2020c).

Ethiopia has registered only 12% of births, 7% of deaths, 6% of marriages, and 5% of divorces since 2016 (EPHI and Ministry of Health, 2019; Gizaw, 2020). The MOH has designed, developed, and implemented several key digital systems, including DHIS2 to manage the national reporting system, e-CHIS to support community health information systems, and MFR to manage and uniquely identify health facilities. Each individual who receives services in a health facility must have a folder kept in the medical record department with a unique (at least at that specific facility) individual medical record number (MRN).

According to the compiled health workforce (Medical doctors, Nurses and Midwifery) data obtained from MOH, the health professional-to-population ratio was 1.74 and 1.81 per 1,000 population in 2018 and 2019, respectively. These health professionals have been trained in accredited educational institutions. Accreditation is a mandatory requirement for higher education institutions in Ethiopia and is managed by the Higher Education Relevance and Quality Agency (HERQA). Health science and medical students who complete training programs based on training standards and curricula are awarded certificates of completion that have to be provided by the training institution. The second certificate is a Certificate of Competence (COC) or Qualification. In collaboration with the Ministry of Education, the MOH developed the training standard and assessment tool (qualification exam) for lower and mid-level training courses, which has been in use since 2011.

In relation to financing, primary health facilities in Ethiopia have two major ways of funding, including revenue retention and budget allocated from the national treasury. The majority of the resource used to finance the PHC are sourced from the external world, which makes the system dependent on foreign aid and support. All the finance of primary health care service delivery units are managed in collaboration with the finance and economic cooperation office. These offices use an electronic financial recording systems to document financial transactions in the primary health care facility.

Overall, the challenges related to major inputs include limited availability of resources, delayed and interrupted distribution of supplies, misdistribution of human resources across PHC facilities, and lack of capacity for equipment maintenance.

Population Health and Facility Management

Ethiopia's health system in the population health and facility management domain is described by features such as, local priority setting that emphasizes a "community first" approach; community engagement through Women's Development Armies (WDA); a progressively developing community-based health information system and community based health insurance systems. On the other hand, campaign-based community outreach; a "family health team" at the community level, a health care financing strategy that outlines the legal framework for facility management; and annual reviews of health system performance

that emphasize one report, along with hierarchical, supportive supervision are integral components of this domain.

In terms of population health, the community engages in local priority setting in different ways despite limited participation. The PHC facilities have a governing board with community representatives who participate in making major decisions regarding local priority problems and strategies. A volunteer community system called WDA has close contact with HEWs and plays a pivotal role in community participation in their health issues. The main challenge here is most of the priorities are set centrally at the national or sub-national level and the community's says are not well recognized. Records like the community-based health insurance (CBHI) and HEWs family folders can be considered as practices of empanelment. Of course, especially the record by the CBHI is very limited, given that CBHI enrolment is low in the country.

Moreover, there is a well-documented facility organization and management system in the country's health authorities. Some of the features include: the Ethiopian Health Center Reform Implementation Guideline (EHCRIG) outlines the organizational structure of PHCUs based on a case-team arrangement; there are clear governance and administrative chains in PHC facilities; Ethiopia has been demonstrated to have nationally standardized comprehensive Health Management Information System (HMIS); and there are continuous supportive supervisions. There are, however, challenges when it comes to practice. For instance, there are several issues regarding the trustworthiness of information obtained from HMIS for decision-making; there are irregularities and capacity issues in the supportive supervision practices.

Overall PHC capacity scores by domains

The PHC assessment indicated that the Ethiopian PHC capacity is in the medium category, with minimal score variability in the MOH and national average scores. In the governance domain, the capacity was rated 2.8 in the MOH assessment, and the national average was 2.5, both out of 4. In the inputs domain, the PHC capacity was rated 2.3 in the MOH and 2.2 was the national average. In population, health and facility management domain on the other hand, the PHC capacity in the MOH was rated 2, and the national average was 2.1 (Table 4).

When we see the sub-national results if the capacity assessment, in the governance domain, the Dire Dawa city administration scored the highest, and the Somali region scored the lowest. The Sidama region had the lowest score in quality management infrastructure, while the Afar and Amhara regions had the lowest scores in priority setting. On the other hand, the Afar, Harari, and Somali regions have the lowest scores in innovation and learning. Dire Dawa had the highest scores in social accountability measures (Table 4).

In the inputs domain, drugs and supplies and facility infrastructure scored in the lowest category, while information systems, workforce and funds were in the medium category. The overall score for the inputs domain was relatively higher for the Addis Ababa, Dire Dawa, Harari, and Amhara regions. The Afar, Benishangul-Gumuz, Gambella, Somali and Sidama regions had lower scores for this domain. All regions and both city administrations scored lowest for the civil registration and vital statistics system. Most regions also scored low on workforce density and distribution. However, the availability of community health workers (HEWs), financial management and information systems also had the highest score in most regions (Table 4).

The Afar, Amhara, Benishangul-Gumuz, and Somali regions had lower scores for the population health and facility management domain. Although most regions had better scores in supportive supervision, and the

two city administrations had better team-based organization, most regions scored low on other facility organization and management measures. In addition, scores for empanelment and proactive population outreach were low for most of the regions (Table 4).

Table 4: PHC capacity assessment final scores at regional and MOH levels

Domain/subdomain/measure	Addis	Afar	Amhara	Ben_Gumz	Dire Dawa	Gambella	Harari	Oromia	Sidama	SNNP	Somali	National average	MOH
Governance	2.7	2.2	2.2	2.8	3.1	2.9	2.2	2.6	2.3	2.6	2.1	2.5	2.8
Governance and Leadership	3	2.6	2.4	3.2	3.6	2.8	2.4	2.6	2.2	2.8	2.2	2.7	3
1: PHC policies (1/2)	3	3	3	3	4	4	3	3	3	3	2	3.1	4
2: PHC policies (2/2) – Leadership	3	2	2	3	3	3	2	2	2	3	2	2.5	3
3: Quality management infrastructure	3	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	1	3	3	2.9	3
4: Social accountability (1/2)	3	3	2	3	4	2	2	2	2	3	2	2.5	3
5: Social accountability (2/2) - Multi-sectoral action	3	2	2	3	4	2	3	3	3	2	2	2.6	2
Adjustment to Population Health Needs	2.3	1.7	2	2.3	2.7	3	2	2.7	2.3	2.3	2	2.3	2.7
6: Surveillance	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2.9	3
7: Priority setting	2	1	1	2	3	3	2	3	2	2	2	2.1	3
8: Innovation and learning	2	1	2	2	2	3	1	2	2	2	1	1.8	2
Inputs	2.5	1.5	2.3	1.8	3	1.9	3.3	2	1.7	2.1	1.6	2.2	2.3
Drugs and Supplies	2.3	1	1.3	1	2.7	1.3	3.7	1	1	1	1	1.6	1
9: Availability of essential medicines & consumable commodities	3	1	2	1	4	1	4	1	1	1	1	1.8	1
10: Basic equipment	3	1	1	1	3	1	4	1	1	1	1	1.6	1
11: Diagnostic supplies	1	1	1	1	4	2	3	1	1	1	1	1.5	1
Facility Infrastructure	3	1	1.7	1	3	1.7	3.3	1.7	1	1.7	1	1.8	1.7
12: Facility distribution	3	1	3	1	4	3	4	3	1	3	1	2.5	3
13: Facility amenities	3	1	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	1	1	1.5	1
14: Standard safety precautions & equipment	3	1	1	1	3	1	3	1	1	1	1	1.5	1
Information Systems	2	2	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.3	2	2	2.3	2	2.2	2
15: Civil registration and vital statistics	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
16: HMIS	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	3.1	3
17: Personal care records	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2.5	2
Workforce	2	1.8	3	2.3	3.3	2.3	3.5	2.5	1.8	2.8	2.5	2.5	3
18: Workforce density and distribution	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	1	1	1	1	1.3	1
19: QA of PHC workforce	2	2	3	2	4	2	3	2	1	3	3	2.5	3
20: PHC workforce competencies	2	2	4	2	4	3	4	3	1	3	4	2.9	4
21: Community health workers	2	4	4	4	4	2	4	4	4	4	2	3.5	4
Funds	3.3	1.7	3.3	2.3	3.7	2	3.7	3	2.7	2.7	1.7	2.7	3.7
22: Facility budgets	3	2	3	2	4	2	4	4	3	3	1	2.8	4
23: Financial MIS	4	1	4	3	4	2	4	3	3	3	1	2.9	4

24: Remuneration	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	2.5	3
Population Health and Facility Management	2.6	1.8	1.3	1.9	3	2.6	2.3	2.3	2.2	2.3	1.3	2.1	2
Population Health Management	2.8	1.8	1.3	1.8	3.5	2.5	2	2	1.5	2.3	1.3	2.1	1.8
25: Local priority setting	3	2	1	1	4	3	2	3	2	2	2	2.3	2
26: Community engagement	3	2	2	3	4	3	2	3	1	3	1	2.5	2
27: Empanelment	1	2	1	1	3	1	1	1	2	3	1	1.5	2
28: Proactive population outreach	4	1	1	2	3	3	3	1	1	1	1	1.9	1
Facility Organization and Management	2.4	1.8	1.4	2	2.4	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.8	2.4	1.4	2.2	2.2
29: Team-based care organization	4	2	1	1	4	3	3	2	3	1	2	2.4	4
30: Facility Mx capability & leadership	1	1	1	3	1	2	2	3	2	2	1	1.7	1
31: Information system use	2	1	1	1	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	1.6	1
32: Performance measurement & Mx (1/2)	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	3	3	2	1	1.6	1
33: Performance measurement & Mx (2/2) – Supportive Supervision	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	2	3.6	4

Color codes Green=4, Yellow=2-3; Red=1

Comparison between national average and MOH scores

We compared the national average (average score of all the regions) assessment scores with the MOH assessment scores for each measure. Except for a few measures, the gap between the regional average and the MOH scores was less than one point. In the proactive population outreach measure, the MOH score exceeded the regional score by 1.6. Other measures, like community health workers, facility budgets and QA of the PHC workforce, were also higher by about one point in the MOH scores (Figure 1). However, there was no significant difference between the two. The two-sample Wilcoxon rank-sum (Mann-Whitney) test indicated that there was no significant difference between the two groups (p-value = 0.69).

Figure 1: The gap between the Ministry of Health and the national average scores

We also compared the national average and MOH scores at domain and sub-domain levels. In the domain scores, the highest difference was seen in the governance domain, with 2.8 for the MOH versus 2.5 for the national average. The sum of the disparities between the MOH and national domain scores was 0.3. The MOH score exceeded the national average by 0.3. The difference in sub-domain scores was as high as 1 in the funds sub-domain, and the national average and MOH scores were equal in the facility organization and management sub-domain.

Comparison of capacity assessment scores across regions

The Dire Dawa city administration scored better and the Somali region scored lower in the governance domain. The gap between the highest and the lowest regional capacity scores was 1. Compared to the other regions, Harari's PHC was better in inputs, with a score of 3.3 out of 4. The Harari region is better than the lowest Afar region by 1.8. On the other hand, Dire Dawa scored the highest in the population health and facility management domain. Amhara and Somali scored the lowest (1.3) in the population health and facility management domain. Generally, Dire Dawa and Addis Ababa are in a good balance for all three domains.

All the regions are in a similar category in the governance and leadership sub-domain. The same is true in the adjustment to population needs sub-domain except for Afar, which scored 1.7. A relatively similar pattern was observed in the four sub-domains under the inputs domain. For instance, in the drugs and

supplies and facility infrastructure sub-domains, all the regions were under the lowest score category except the two city administrations and the Harari region. In the information systems, workforce, and funds sub-domains, almost all regions were in the medium category except for Afar, which is in the lowest category in workforce and funds. Much variability among regions was observed in the two sub-domains of the population health and facility management domain. More than half (six) of the regions are in the medium category and the rest are in the lowest category in the population health management sub-domain. The Afar, Amhara and Somali regions scored in the lowest category, while all the others scored in the medium category for the facility organization and management sub-domains (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Regional capacity assessment average scores and 95% confidence interval.

Discussion

We carried out this study to measure the capacity of PHC in Ethiopia using the PHC progression model. Ethiopia's PHC capacity is at a medium level in all domains. In fact, the PHC in the governance domain has a better status compared to the others; similarly, the PHC in the inputs domain is better than the population health and facility management domain. Comparing the PHC capacity assessment results at the federal and sub-national levels showed relatively similar results in all three domains. Using the PHC progression model, the study findings indicated that the overall capacity of the Ethiopian PHC in terms of governance was 2.8 out of four, in terms of input was 2.3 out of four and in terms of population health and facility management was 2 out of four. The scores of the ministry of health assessment were not significantly different from the scores of the national average.

With a domain score of 2.8 at the federal level and an average score of 2.5 at the regional level, the governance of PHC in Ethiopia is characterized by the availability of important policy and strategy, social accountability, and quality management documents at the national level. The PHC capacity was scored medium consistently for all the regions, with a maximum score in Dire Dawa (3.1) and a minimum score in Somali (2.1). The contextualized implementation of national policies in regions and the strengthening of PHC leadership at sub-regional levels is not consistent with the higher levels (Ethiopian Ministry of Health, 2015). Similar studies performed in various African countries have governance scores close to the current study, ranging from 2.4 in Senegal to 2.9 in Tanzania (PHCPI, 2018d, 2018b, 2018e). In Rwanda, however, the governance domain score was 3.5 out of 4 (PHCPI, 2018c), which is higher than the scores in our studies and other similar studies done in Africa.

Ethiopia's PHC was rated medium (2.3) in terms of inputs relevant to PHC activities. The national input score and the regional average were equivalent. This domain was characterized by a complex picture of availability, distribution, and quality of inputs. At the national level, health facilities have nearly 50% availability of essential medicines, basic equipment, basic amenities, standard precautions for infection prevention, and limited availability of diagnostic tests (Ethiopian Public Health Institute, 2018). Due to the rapid expansion of health facilities, access to primary health coverage increased from 50.7% in 2000 to more than 90% in 2019 (Ethiopian Public Health Institute, 2018; EPHI and Ministry of Health, 2019). There is 57% facility-based notification and 18–20% community-based notification of births and deaths (Ethiopian Public Health Institute (EPHI), Ethiopian Federal Ministry of Health and ICF International, 2014; Ethiopian Public Health Institute, 2017). Similar studies indicated the input scores range from 2.6 in Rwanda to 2.1 in Senegal (PHCPI, 2018d, 2018b, 2018c, 2018e). All scores, including Ethiopia's, are in the same category.

Sub-nationally, regions classified as least developed, including Afar, Gambella, Benishangul-Gumuz and Somali, and the newly established region, Sidama, have low capacity in inputs relevant to PHC. The Ethiopian SARA assessment has also discovered that the overall availability of inputs and basic amenities is low in the four developing regions (Ethiopian Public Health Institute, 2018).

There is promising progress toward the minimum threshold of the health professionals to population ratio of 2.3 per 1000 people in Ethiopia, the 2025 benchmark set by the WHO for Sub-Saharan Africa (Anyangwe and Mtonga, 2007). However, critical gaps in health workforce distribution and quality remain to be addressed. The inputs domain of PHC is also characterized by recent health financing reforms in revenue retention and utilization that have improved the availability of funds for health infrastructure and supplies;

the utilization of an electronic (IBEX) financial management system to manage and track budgets allocated from the government; and variations in the predictability and timing of overtime payments for health workers across regions (Xu Ke, James Chris *et al.*, 2014).

Ethiopia's PHC scored medium (2) in the population health and facility management domain. The national score and regional average scores are almost similar. In this regard, Ethiopia's PHC system is characterized by the local priority setting through a district-based planning approach (Ministry of Health, 2021). Although they are not currently operating well in the country, the Women's Development Army is a strong link for a systematic community engagement approach (Yitbarek, Abraham and Morankar, 2019). Furthermore, there is a progressive trend in community-based health information systems and community-based health insurance (Ministry of Health, 2011). A recently established system called the "family health team" at the community level and a healthcare financing strategy that outlines the legal framework for facility management are key issues in the current PHC of the country (Ministry of Health, 2016). Even though they are not too far apart, the population health and facility management scores of other African countries' PHC systems are consistently higher than Ethiopia's. Their scores range from 2.1 in Tanzania to 2.7 in Ghana (PHCPI, 2018d, 2018b, 2018e). However, Rwanda's PHC scored 3.1 out of 4 (PHCPI, 2018c), which is higher than all of the African countries' scores.

In agreement with the inputs domain, the capacity of PHC in the least developed regions of Afar, Benihangul Gumuz, and Somali is low. These findings are relatively consistent with many health and health-related indicators in the country (Ministry of Health, 2019, 2020a, 2021). Furthermore, unlike other domains, the PHC of Amhara region has scored the least in the Population Health and Facility Management domain. This result was because there was low status of proactive population outreach services, keeping recorded family needs in a standard document in the region. In addition, the habit of analyzing and using information for decision-making, capacity building endeavors of PHC practitioners and leaders is at its lowest stage.

Implications

The Ethiopian health system, including the health policy and strategies, focused on prevention and promotion interventions. This made the PHC a hub for implementing national policies and strategies. Capable PHC in all dimensions is needed to achieve national goals like the rolling HSTP goals. An intermediate capacity in terms of governance, inputs and population health and facility management is insufficient to achieve national and international goals. This is bi-directionally linked with achieving universal health coverage. Since PHC is a strategy meant to ensure universal health coverage throughout the country, it is a great move to identify gaps in capacity and recommend possible solutions.

Strength and Limitations

The PHC capacity assessment using the PHC progression model is new, and this assessment is the first in Ethiopia. We used a robust method and procedure to conduct the study. Similar studies were previously conducted in various countries using the PHC progression model (PHCPI, 2018d, 2018b, 2018c, 2018e, 2018a). The studies were conducted at the central level, in the MOH or equivalent organ of the country. In our study, however, we conducted the study at the MOH and sub-national (regional) settings. Moreover, we used well-trained and experienced health systems specialists as external assessors; we addressed both the national and subnational health systems to get full insights about the country's PHC; we used multiple

data sources to obtain relevant data. Although we used a robust method to come up with a final score, most of the internal, external, and consensus scores were subjective. That might compromise the objectivity of the findings. Furthermore, the PHC capacity assessment was mostly based on federal and regional levels. That might not show a clear picture of what is happening at the PHC facilities.

Conclusion and recommendations

In conclusion, this assessment has revealed the key strengths and weaknesses of the PHC capacity in the country. The findings indicated that, about governance, there are relevant PHC policies and leadership structures at the federal and regional levels. However, the capacity to effectively implement these policies and strategies at those levels is sub-optimal and needs strengthening. The challenges related to major inputs include limited availability of resources, delayed and interrupted supply of drugs and supplies, maldistribution of human resources across PHC facilities, and lack of capacity for maintenance of equipment. With the promising recent progress of health management information, attention needs to be paid to further improvement of data quality and utilization of information for local decision-making.

To improve the management efficiency at PHC facilities, the capabilities of PHC facility and district health office managers should be enhanced through on-the-job training, continuing professional development, and supportive supervision. Given the critical role of development partners in supporting PHC in Ethiopia, the MOH and Regional Health Bureaus need to improve the coordination of this support and focus on areas with high levels of inequities in delivering PHC services.

There is a need for periodic assessment of PHC capacity to regularly evaluate progress, identify gaps, and develop strategies to strengthen PHC capacity further to move towards universal health coverage.

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